

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B253
Date: 14 December 2006
Take Off: 10:28:44Z
Landing: 15:42:02Z
Flight Time: 5h13m18

Campaign: WINTEX – StratoCumulus

Operating Area: Chilbolton and SW

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Steven Abel	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist 2	Richard Cotton	Met Office
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Flight Track:

B253 Track 14-DEC-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b253
 Date: 14 Dec 2006
 Project: WINTEX SCu
 Location: Chilbolton & Boscombe

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
091326		Start-Up	0.18 kft	125	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
100034		INU	0.18 kft	125	To Navigate
102844		T/O	1.7 kft	303	Cranfield
104219		Videos	10.0 kft	244	Start FFC and DFC
105908	110258	Profile 1	10.0 - 6.2 kft	205	1000fpm
110405	110510	Profile 1	6.2 - 5.2 kft	026	QFE 1008 500fpm
110516	111012	Profile 1	5.1 - 2.7 kft	027	Interrupt at 2.5k'
111128	111221	Profile 1	2.7 - 2.2 kft	249	2.5k'-2k'
111831	112202	Profile 1	2.2 - 0.19 kft	231	2k'- 50' Boscombe
112202	112949	Profile 2	0.19 - 5.5 kft	228	50' from Boscombe
113146	113651	Profile 3	5.5 - 2.5 kft	076	2300'
113651	113802	Run 1.1	2.5 kft	046	2300' Inbound
114244	114825	Run 1.2	2.5 kft	239	2300' Outbound
114628		Heimann	2.5 kft	232	Cal
115450	115946	Run 2.1	3.0 kft	077	2800' Inbound
120204	121020	Run 2.2	3.0 kft	236	2800' Outbound
121307	121812	Run 3.1	3.5 kft	055	3300' 240M radial
121333		Heimann	3.5 kft	061	Cal
121621		Videos	3.5 kft	054	Change Tapes
122147	123021	Run 3.2	3.5 - 3.4 kft	231	3300' Inbound
123435		Heimann	4.0 kft	120	Cal @3800'
123509	124010	Run 4.1	3.9 kft	076	3800' Inbound
123810		Event	3.9 kft	088	Avoiding Action
124613	125238	Run 4.2	4.0 - 4.5 kft	227	3800' Outbound
125948	130418	Run 5	4.4 - 4.5 kft	063	4300' Inbound
130051		Heimann	4.5 kft	068	Cal
130801	131605	Run 6.1	2.2 kft	215	2000' Outbound
130904		Heimann	2.2 kft	247	Cal
131935	132434	Run 6.2	2.1 kft	045	2000' Inbound
132809	133842	Profile 4	2.2 - 10.0 kft	238	From 2k',500fpm
134824		Videos	10.0 kft	211	Change Tapes
135045	135520	Profile 5	9.9 - 6.2 kft	237	Interrupt @ 6k'
135641	135833	Profile 5	6.2 - 5.0 kft	016	1000fpm to 5k'
135844	135903	Profile 5	4.9 - 4.7 kft	042	500fpm from 5k'
140009	140253	Profile 5	4.6 - 3.2 kft	010	4.5k'- 3k'
141022	141343	Profile 5	3.2 - 2.2 kft	342	3k', QFE 1007
141720	142057	Profile 5	2.2 - 0.19 kft	233	2k' - 50'
142057	142610	Profile 6	0.19 - 4.4 kft	228	50'-4k', 500fpm Ovhd Boscombe
142625	142759	Profile 6	4.6 - 6.2 kft	230	1000fpm
143019		Heimann	6.2 kft	253	Cal
143640	143853	Profile 7	6.2 - 4.2 kft	255	1000fpm -4k'
144124	144437	Profile 7	4.2 - 2.2 kft	093	4k'- 2k'
144437	145441	Run 7	2.2 kft	092	2000' Inbound
150030	150557	Run 8	2.7 kft	228	2500' Outbound
150106		Heimann	2.7 kft	230	Cal
150848	151237	Run 9	3.2 kft	027	3000' Inbound
151700		Videos	7.1 kft	063	End of Tapes
154202		Land	0.20 kft	352	Cranfield
154632		Shutdown	0.19 kft	308	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B253 Track 14-DEC-06

WINTEX Sortie Brief: Stratocumulus measurements

Date : 14 Dec 2006

Flight Number : B253

Mission Scientist : S.Abel / R.Cotton

Sortie Aims: The principal aim of this sortie is to obtain measurements of the vertical and horizontal structure together with microphysical properties of stratocumulus cloud in the vicinity of the Chilbolton radar site and over sea areas around the SW peninsula. The measurements will be used to verify remotely-sensed values of a number of parameters (cloud base and top, cloud LWC and LWP, drizzle LWC and drop size spectrum, turbulence within and below the cloud layer) that are obtained using combinations of radar and lidar measurements. The measurements may also be combined with observations from Cardington and other sites to describe the evolution of a Sc layer over land.

Sortie Location: In the vicinity of the Chilbolton observatory, Hampshire and sea areas around the SW peninsula.

Communications: Chilbolton radar ("RADSEARCH") on 130.575 MHz.

Weather conditions: A layer of stratocumulus that extends over the Chilbolton site. An absence of medium / upper cloud is preferred but not essential. Wind direction between about 225 and 280 degrees true.

Instrument requirements:

- JW / Nevzorov to be zeroed when in clear air at any altitude when straight / level.
- Cloud physics console. Normal operation of all probes
- CDP - operating
- Turbulence probe – monitor performance when in icing conditions.

Sortie detail:

- (a) T+0 Take-off Cranfield, transit to operating area at FL100 or above (40 min)
- (b) T+40 Profile descent 1000ft/min from transit altitude to minimum permitted altitude – missed approach to Boscombe Down. Note top and base altitudes of Sc layer. If cloud top is 500ft or more *above* the safety altitude (2300ft amsl) then in-cloud runs over Chilbolton are possible (10 min).
- (c) T+60 straight / level leg of 5 min oriented along a radial within ~10 deg of mean wind direction towards radar and finishing overhead the site. Procedure turn to reverse heading. Repeat the 5 min straight / level leg, commencing run start prior to passing outbound over the radar site. Procedure turn. (18 min)
- (d) Flight patterns at (c) to be flown at altitudes: Cloudbase – 500ft, Cloudbase + 500ft, mid-cloud-layer, Cloudtop – 300ft. Altitudes also selected on advice from Radsearch (Minimum time 80min)
- (e) T+140 If cloud conditions permit continued operations in Chilbolton area, then items c) and d) may be repeated.
- (f) Otherwise, transit to sea area upwind (ideally Lyme Bay but otherwise, to the SW of Lands End) Profile descent at 500ft/min from Cloudtop + 1000ft to minimum permitted. (15min)
- (g) T+155 Commence stack of straight / level legs of 10 min duration, orientation acrosswind preferred. Minimum number of altitudes to be flown:

- 500ft asl, Cloudbase – 500ft, Cloudbase +500ft, mid-cloud-level, Cloudtop – 500ft, Cloudtop + 1000ft. Others may be flown at Mission Scientist discretion. (70min min)
- (h) T+225 Sawtooth profile acrosswind. Max.altitude Cloudtop + 500ft, min altitude Cloudbase – 1000ft. Ascent / descent rate 1000ft/min. Straight/level duration 1 min between climbs/descents. Aim to complete 2 full cycles of climb/descent. (20min)
- (j) T+245 Repeat legs from (g) as time permits.
- (k) T+275 Return transit
- (l) T+315 Land

Figure 1. The location of microwave radiometer measurements to measure Liquid Water Path at Weybourne, RAF Marham, Cardington (Bedford). The radar/lidar site at Chilbolton is also shown.

Mission Scientist Debrief

WINTEX Stratocumulus measurements in the vicinity of the Chilbolton radar

Flight: B253

Date: 14th December 2006

Mission Scientist: Steve Abel

Summary of brief Remote sensing instrumentation at the Chilbolton observatory is used to derive values of a number of parameters such as cloud base and top, cloud LWC and LWP, drizzle LWC and drop size spectrum, turbulence within and below the cloud layer. This principal aim of this flight was to obtain in-situ measurements of the structure and microphysical properties of stratocumulus in the vicinity of the Chilbolton radar to validate these retrievals. The measurements can also be combined with observations downwind to study the evolution of the stratocumulus layer over land.

General cloud characteristics The outbound transit showed that there was extensive Sc with a few holes. Cirrus above but no mid-cloud. The stratocumulus persisted throughout the observing period. The observations showed a much higher and more pronounced inversion than forecast by the Met Office model which allowed the maintenance of a deeper cloud layer than expected. Cloud top was around 4000 ft and cloud base around 1400 ft. This flight could therefore also provide an interesting case study for the forecast model.

Overview of flight pattern

1. Missed approach at Boscombe Down to characterise the vertical structure of the Sc. Both the descent and following ascent through the cloud layer were at 500 fpm. Profile descent had to be interrupted several times due to air traffic.
2. Series of 5 minute SLRs at various altitudes both inbound and outbound of Chilbolton. SLRs flown at altitudes of 2300 ft (x2) 2800 ft (x2) 3300 ft (x2) 3800 ft (x2) 4300 ft (x1) 2000 ft (x2). Wind direction approx 240 deg. For the first 2/3 runs we were unable to contact the radar which was pointing along the 252 radial. Contact made in R2.1 and radar repositioned to point along 240 radial. Note that SLRs were done along the 240 degree radial although deviations from this course were made at times due to air traffic.
3. Profile ascent to FL100 for comfort break. Ascent rate 500 fpm until 1000 ft above cloud tops.
4. Second missed approach at Boscombe Down to characterise the vertical structure of the Sc. Both the descent and following ascent through the cloud layer were at 500 fpm. Profile descent had to be interrupted several times due to air traffic.
5. Inbound run to Chilbolton at 2000 ft. Run length extended to 10 mins to get better statistics on horizontal structure. Only able to do at one altitude due to time constraints.
6. Two final 5 minute SLRs at 2500 and 3000 ft.

Summary The stratocumulus was well-observed by both the aircraft and Radars/lidars at

Chilbolton (plus Larkhil sondes). It was not possible to do a SLR completely underneath the Sc deck due to altitude limitations although there were occasions when the aircraft popped in and out of cloud when doing a run near cloud base (due to the variability in cloud base level). In addition there were a good set of sondes released from Cardington to look at downstream evolution.

Instrumentation issues

2D-C: U/S Would have been useful for measurements of the drizzle drop spectrum

FFSSP: New electronics having some problems. Multiple counting of particles and bit shift in the time stamp. May be difficult to extract useful data.

The CDP and SID-2 probes appeared to work well and will provide data of the drop size spectrum.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B253** Date **14/12/06** Name **STEVE ASEK** Page **1** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
103000	T10				Cranfield. Cloud base ~ FLO20
103600	Transit				Cloud top ~ FLO35
					Extensive SC (few holes around)
					Cirrus above. No mid-cloud
105908	P1↓	FLO40	20.5	51.2N 1.4W	Commence missed approach
110258	P1↓	FLO60			Interrupt profile at Boscombe Down
110405	P1↓	FLO60			Restart profile
		Be			Cloud top ~ FLO39
					Cloud base
					Descent rate 500'pm through cloud
	P1↓	FLO25			Interrupt profile
					Just above cloud base
111128	P1↓	FLO25			Restart profile
111221	P1↓	FLO20			Interrupt
					Still in cloud. Constant altitude for few mins until reach Boscombe Down
111632		FLO20			Just above CB
111831	P1↓	FLO20			Restart profile
					CB ~ FLO13 - FLO14
112208	P2↑	50'			End P1↓ Start P2↑
					Cloud base ~ 1400'
					Gap at ~ 2000' but cloud around us. Looks like 2 layers possibly.
					Cloud top at 3800'
112949	P2↑	FLOSS			End profile
113146	P3↓	FLOSS			Start profile to 2300'
					for initial run to Chilbolton

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.253** Date **14/12/06** Name **STEVE ABEL** Page **2** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Cloud top 3600'
					Winds ~ 240
113651	P3 ↓	2300'			End profile and start run
"	R1	2300'			to Chilbolton. Just above cloud base
113802	R1	2300'			END. Still no answer from RADSEARCH
114244	R1.2 R2	2300'	234		Over Chilbolton Wind 240 Just above CB. Occasionally see surface
114825	R1.2	2300'			End Next runs at 2800'
115450	R2.1	2800'			Inbound run to Chilbolton Air traffic taking us away from overhead slightly Contacted RADSEARCH
115946	R2.1	2800'			Flying along 240 radial. Re-aiming radar. (pres 252)
120204	R2.2	2800'			Mid-cloud run.
121020	R2.2	2800'			Next run at 3300'
121307	R3.1	3300'			START Wind 240 Just skipping in and out of cloud tops ~ 121600
121812	R3.1	3300'			End
122147	R3.2	3300'			Just below cloud tops
122330					Air traffic taken us off the 240 radial by 2 miles

~~End of~~ of -

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B253**..... Date **14/12/06** Name **STEVE ABEL** Page **3** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
122557					Back onto track at 12 miles from Chilbolton.
123021	R3.2	3300'	END		End run.
123509	R4.1	3800'	START		In and out of tops at 3800' after ascent. Again air traffic taking us off radial.
					1.7 miles S Chilbolton on overhead pass
124010	R4.1	3800'	END		Radar reports waves on length scale of ~15km
					Passing to North of Chilbolton due to air traffic
124613	R4.2	3800'	START		Drizzle on windshield
					In and out of cloud tops. Evidence of wave structure in vertical velocity profile. Length scale ~12km
125238	R4.2	3800'	END		Next run at 4300' above most cloud tops by several hundred feet. Odd cell punching up to this alt.
123948	R5	4300'	START		In and out of cloud tops
					Large sections of this run above clouds.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B253**..... Date **14/12/06** Name **STEVE ABEL** Page **4** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
130618	R5	4300'			END run. Descending to minimum alt @ 2000'
					Just above cloud base
130801	R6.1	2000'	START		Just passed South of Chilbolton. Could see Chilbolton. In and out of cloud. Some drizzle sized drops on 2D-P. 2D-C out of action.
131320					Below cloud base.
131605	R6.1	2000'	END		Cloud base undulating
131935	R6.2	2000'	START		Inbound to Chilbolton
					Just above cloud base
					Radar pointing up as we pass ~ $\frac{1}{2}$ mile South.
132434	R6.2	2000'	END		← We are below cloud base here
132809	P4↑	2000'	START		Ascend to FL100 for comfort break. 500' per whil ~1000' above cloud top
					Cloud to ~ 4000'
134008	P4↑	FL100	END		
135045	P5↓	FL100	START		Descend for Missed approach at Boscombe Down.
135520	P5↓	FL060	Interrupt profile		Extensive Sc in all
135641	P5↓	FL060	Restart profile		directions

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B253**..... Date **14.1.2.06** Name **STEVE ASKE** Page **5** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
135903	PS↓	FLO45		Interrupt profile	Above cloud tops
140009	PS↓	FLO45		Restart profile	Cloud top ~ FLO38
	PS↓	FLO30			Possible 2 layer structure
140253	PS↓	FLO30		Interrupt profile	Looks like there may be broken cloud field below us with gap then thicker layer above
141022	PS↓	FLO30		Restart profile	
141343	PS↓	FLO20		Interrupt profile	Just above cloud base
141720	PS↓	FLO20		Restart	Cloud base ~ 1700'
142057	PS↓	P6↑ 50'			Profile ascent to FLO60 then restart Chilbolton legs
142759	P6↑	FLO60		END	Cloud base ~ 1500' Sc in all directions to horizon.
143640	P7↓	FLO60		START	Profile descent to 2000'. Followed by inbound run to Chilbolton. Extended run to 10 mins instead of 5.
143853	P7↓	FLO60		INTERUPT	
144124	P7↓	FLO60		RESTART	Cloud top ~ 3000'
144435	P7	2000'			In cloud.
144435	R7.1	2000'			Inbound run to Chilbolton Sc Mid-cloud level On 240 radial again winds 230 ⁰

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B253

Date: 06/12/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:32:00						Off											
10:59:13	5	0.09	44	1												Start Profile 1 from FL100	
11:00:31	10	0.09														FL090	
11:01:20	13	0.08														FL080	
11:02:14	13	0.08														FL070	
11:02:59	13	0.08														FL060	
11:05:20	15	0.08														FL050	
11:07:20	10	0.09	45	100	1000			Noise								FL040	
11:09:36	25	0.32	Reset	2000	2000			Noise								FL030	
11:18:59	80	0.22	707	2000	3000			Noise								FL020	
11:22:00	185	0.09	735	20	1											End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 from 50'	
11:23:18	180	0.08	736	80	10			100	200							FL010	
11:24:55	90	0.11	810	1000	20			20								FL020	
11:26:24	65	0.16	908	1500	2000			500								FL030	
11:27:44	15	0.09	985													FL040	
11:29:49	15	0.11														End of Profile 2 @ FL055	
11:31:46	15	0.09														Start Profile 3 from FL055	
11:33:45	18	0.11														FL40	
11:36:52																End of Profile 3 & Start Run 1.1 @ 2300'	
11:37:00	70	0.16	1239	2000	2000			30									
11:38:03																End of Run 1.1	
11:42:46																Start Run 1.2 @ 2300'	
11:43:00	50	0.16	2036	3000	5000			30									
11:45:00	100	0.18	Reset	3000	5000			30									
11:47:00	40	0.11	330	2500	5000			10									
11:48:25																End of Run 1.2	
11:54:54			Reset													Start Run 2.1 @ 2800'	
11:55:00	140	0.25	98	2500	9000			35									
11:57:00	105	0.20	234	2000	5000												
11:59:00	80	0.27	428	3000	9000			50									
11:59:52																End of Run 2.1	
12:02:05																Start Run 2.2 @ 28000'	
12:03:00	70	0.24	1079	3000	3000			230									
12:05:00	70	0.29	1341	2000	2000			15									
12:07:00	125	0.34	1653	2500	5000			400									
12:09:00	65	0.34	1895	2000	Fail			100									
12:10:20																End of Run	
12:13:10																Start Run 3.1 @ 3300'	
12:14:00	105	0.30	2500	3000	8000			375									
12:16:00	170	0.36	3004	3000	5000			135									
12:18:16																End of Run 3.1	
12:21:48																Start Run 3.2 @ 3300'	
12:22:00	200	0.27	3724	2000	6000			200									
12:24:00	180	0.38	4054	2000	4000			15									
12:26:00	100	0.39	4261	2500	5000			600									
12:28:00	160	0.29	4624	2000	3000			2000									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B253

Date: 06/12/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:30:26																End of Run 3.2	
12:35:10																Start Run 4.1 @ 3800'	
12:36:00	20	0.10	5195	3000	6000			170									
12:38:00	160	0.36	5486	3000	5000			65	200						12		
12:40:11																End of Run 4.1	
12:46:13																Start Run 4.2 @ 3800'	
12:47:00	180	0.28	6504	3000	5000			150	200						12		
12:49:00	180	0.37	6728	3000	4000			125	200						12		
12:51:20	20	0.08	6915	1													
12:52:38																End of Run 4.2	
12:59:51																Start Run 5 @ 4300'	
13:00:00	35	0.11	7206	1													
13:02:00	15	0.11	7245	1													
13:04:19																End of Run 5	
13:08:03																Start Run 6.1 @ 2000'	
13:09:00	130	0.10	7754	30	10												
13:11:00	115	0.13	7947	2000	2000			240	200						12		
13:13:00	100	0.19	8148	2000	100												
13:15:00	45	0.18	8197	1000	1000												
13:16:06																End of Run 6.1	
13:19:34																Start Run 6.2 @ 2000'	
13:20:00	75	0.12	8470	1500	1000			65	200						12		
13:22:00	115	0.10	8698	500	10												
13:24:00	135	0.09	8802	500	200			15	200						12		
13:24:35																End of Run 6.2	
13:28:11																Start Profile 4 from 2000'	
13:29:18	50	0.10	9134	2000	2000			175	200						12	FL030	
13:31:13	80	0.23	9336	10	10											FL040	
13:32:31	20	0.07														FL050	
13:33:43	13	0.10														FL060	
13:35:02	5	0.10														FL070	
13:36:13	20	0.09														FL080	
13:37:37	25	0.10														FL090	
13:38:41	90	0.11														End of Profile 4 @ FL100	
13:50:50	15	0.10	9337													Start Profile 5 from FL100	
13:51:50	12	0.09														FL090	
13:53:06	25	0.10														FL080	
13:54:10	12	0.09														FL070	
13:55:22	10	0.08														FL060	
13:57:04	20	0.09														FL050	
14:01:05	15	0.08														FL040	
14:10:29	60	0.29	10267	3000	3000			8	200						12	FL030	
14:13:20	130	0.09	Reset	1000	1000											FL020	
14:21:07	140	0.10	Reset													End of Profile 5 & Start Profile 6 from 50'	
14:22:02	110	0.09	0	100	1000											FL010	
14:22:50	60	0.18	127	2000	4000			25	200						12	FL020	

Flight:

B253

KEY

Duff Data	
Minor Problems	
	OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
 - BBR (IR) Lower:
 - BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
 - BBR (IR) Upper:
 - BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
 - DEIMOS:
 - IR Camera:
 - JNO2 Lower:
 - JNO2 Upper:
 - JO1D Lower:
 - JO1D Upper:
 - MARSS:
 - SHIMS Lower:
 - SHIMS Upper:
 - SWS:
 - TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
 - NOx TE42C:
 - Ozone TE49C:
 - Ozone TE49:
 - SO2 TE43C:
 - TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 - TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 - FAGE:
 - Formaldehyde:
 - NOxy:
 - ORAC:
 - PAN:
 - PERCA:
 - Peroxide:
 - PTRMS:
 - TDLAS (1C):
 - WAS Bags:
 - WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
 - LIDAR:
 - LTI:
 - SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B253

Date: 14th December 2006

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS – u/s
2. TWC - u/s
3. 2D-C u/s
4. Can't print from "old" laptops as print driver not compatible with Win '95 (i.e. no access via usb).

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H Calls - Nil

B

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 14/12/06

Flight No: B253

Pre-Flighter: PAPJ

Item	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
		Aircraft Cabin		
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
External Checks overleaf				→

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Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps empty (weekly only)		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B253:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting completion of processing
Core Chemistry	pre flight operator only, unmanned in-flight operation (on auto calibrate) so no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2 Feb 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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